

TRUST Principles Use Case

Contact Information

Organization: National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics - INOE 2000

Repository: [INFRA-ART Spectral Library](#)

Contact Person: Ioana Maria Cortea

Email: ioana.cortea@inoe.ro

Introduction

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library is a dynamic, open-access digital repository developed by the National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics – INOE 2000 (Romania). It functions as a FAIR data service supporting the heritage science community by providing access to a wide collection of high-quality spectral datasets on materials commonly found in works of art, archaeological artifacts, and other heritage or cultural goods. This specialized repository currently aggregates over 2,000 curated spectra corresponding to more than 1,000 reference materials, encompassing ATR-FTIR, XRF, Raman, and SWIR reflectance data.

Decision makers: The INFRA-ART Project Coordinator oversees strategic direction, project coordination, and implementation of FAIR data practices.

Stakeholders:

- **Primary users:** Heritage science specialists who use spectroscopic techniques in their professional practice. This group includes researcher, heritage scientist, and conservators, who rely on access to spectral libraries for accurate material identification and comparative analysis.
- **Broader communities:** Educators, cross-disciplinary researchers, students, and potentially the public, who benefit from well-documented, reusable spectral data for research, and education.

Funders: National and European science funding bodies, including UEFISCDI (grant no. PN-III-P1-1.1-PD-2019-1099, PN-IV-P2-2.1-TE-2023-2019), as well as EU-level programs via cascading grants mechanism (FAIR-IMPACT and RDA TIGER projects).

Description

Transparency: The INFRA-ART Spectral Library openly shares its governance structure, data policies, and curation workflows. Publicly available documents include the [Data Access Policy](#), [Data Deposit Policy](#), and [Data Curation Policy](#). These are regularly updated to reflect evolving standards and community best practices, ensuring that users can clearly understand how data is managed, curated, and preserved.

Responsibility: We take active responsibility for the accuracy, integrity, and ethical management of the spectral data we host. Our team ensures compliance with legal and disciplinary norms, and assigns clear roles in data stewardship, curation, and user support.

User Focus: The repository is designed to serve the needs of its users. INFRA-ART provides intuitive tools for search, navigation, and download options. User [support channels](#),

[documentation](#), and [feedback forms](#) encourage active dialogue, making users co-contributors in shaping repository services.

Sustainability: INFRA-ART’s sustainability strategy combines institutional support through the INFRA-ART project with strategic funding plans for maintenance and infrastructure renewal. The repository prioritizes open standards and non-proprietary formats for long-term interoperability. Participation in preservation networks and collaborations—such as the FIDELIS Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories—reinforces sustainability through shared evaluation and peer learning.

Technology: Data integrity and security are supported through backups, access controls, and monitoring. Our commitment is to provide a stable, secure, and user-friendly environment with continuous improvements to ensure long-term access.

Mapping of Metrics

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library applies the TRUST Principles through documented policies and measurable practices, many of which are outlined in our policy framework. Each principle is supported by concrete indicators:

Transparency is demonstrated through openly available governance documents, which are regularly updated. This provides users with clarity on how data is managed, assures funders and policymakers of compliance with international best practices, and gives repository professionals clear workflows.

Responsibility is reflected in clear role assignments, provenance-rich metadata, and compliance with licensing and ethical standards. This ensures users can trust data integrity, while funders see FAIR data stewardship.

User Focus is monitored through feedback mechanisms, responsive support, and continuous improvements to the platform’s user experience. This is complemented by the launch of a dedicated [blog](#) that shares educational resources and guidance, supporting skill development in cross-disciplinary research. Together, these efforts directly benefit users while also demonstrating to funders that the repository is responsive to community needs and impact expectations.

Sustainability is measured by ongoing institutional and project-based funding, adoption of open formats, and participation in trusted repository networks. This reassures both funders and users of continuity and ensures long-term access to data.

Technology is tracked through system uptime, security monitoring, EOSC compliance milestones, and planned integration with infrastructures such as OpenAIRE. This ensures reliable access for users, and demonstrates alignment with European infrastructures to funders.

Implementation / Use

- Why did you implement or use the TRUST Principles?
We adopted the TRUST Principles to align with international best practices, and to strengthen INFRA-ART’s position as a trusted resource for heritage science. Our goal is to ensure that the heritage science community, and the scientific community at large,

can trust the database, reuse its data with confidence, and rely on it as a go-to resource.

- What did you need to think about before you could implement or use the TRUST Principles?
We first considered our governance framework, institutional support, and technical infrastructure. Clear policies were drafted and made openly accessible, while plans were developed to ensure long-term sustainability and interoperability with European infrastructures such as EOSC.
- How did you implement or use the TRUST Principles?
TRUST principles were embedded into our workflows by publishing transparent policies, assigning clear stewardship responsibilities, engaging with users through feedback, and developing a technical roadmap toward EOSC compliance and interoperability with services like OpenAIRE. All key documentation is openly available on [Zenodo](#), and the repository is indexed in trusted registries such as re3data and FAIRsharing, enhancing visibility and community recognition.
- Are there other ways you could have implemented or used the TRUST Principles?
Alternative approaches could have included pursuing formal certification, such as CoreTrustSeal. While this was not part of the initial implementation, it remains a goal for the future as the repository matures.
- What challenges did you face in implementing or using the TRUST Principles?
Challenges included additional workload, balancing technical development with policy writing, and translating international best practices into practical workflows for a relatively small, specialized repository. Building new skills within the team (composed mainly of scientific researchers) was also essential to support ongoing developments (e.g. machine-actionable metadata schemas for enhanced semantic interoperability). Some commitments, such as achieving full FAR/EOSC compliance, remain in progress and require ongoing development, including support from external IT teams.

Stakeholder impact

- Who is using the TRUST Principles?

Policy makers and funders: National and EU funding bodies “use” the TRUST Principles as a benchmark to evaluate whether INFRA-ART is a sustainable, trustworthy, and standards-aligned investment.

Repository professionals: The INFRA-ART team applies the TRUST Principles as a framework for governance, workflows, and skill development. Because our policies are openly shared, other (external) repository professionals can also benefit from and adapt these practices.

Repository users: Heritage scientists, conservators, research professionals, educators, and students benefit directly from TRUST-aligned services, gaining greater confidence in data integrity, transparency, and long-term access.

- How do stakeholders benefit from the implementation or use of the TRUST Principles?

Policy makers and funders: the use of TRUST Principles demonstrates accountability, sustainability, and alignment with European infrastructures (EOSC), giving funders confidence in the long-term value of their investment.

Repository professionals: the implementation of TRUST Principles provides a structured framework for governance and workflows, helping the INFRA-ART team translate best

practices into practical policies, strengthen internal capacity. This structured approach also lays the foundation for pursuing formal certification, such as the CoreTrustSeal, in the future.

Repository users: From a user perspective, the implementation of the TRUST Principles ensures that datasets are reliable, well-documented, and reusable. Users benefit from transparent policies, secure infrastructure, and ongoing technical improvements, which give them greater confidence in data integrity, transparency, and long-term access.

- Was there any hesitancy from stakeholders around implementing or using the TRUST Principles? Describe.

Policy makers and funders: No hesitancy, though we consider that there is an expectation for concrete results (e.g., EOSC alignment, future certification such as CoreTrustSeal) which requires ongoing resources.

Repository professionals: Alignment with the TRUST Principles was voluntarily embraced; however, some hesitancy arose from the additional workload required to translate these principles into practice.

Repository users: Users mainly expect intuitive services rather than insight into governance frameworks. TRUST adds value for them indirectly, through improved reliability and usability of the repository.

Roadmap

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-024-03449-z>

Current repository stage	Description of steps
Introduction (2021)	The repository was launched in 2021 with the aim to provide open access to spectral reference data for the heritage science community. At this stage, the focus was on building a functional service, curating datasets, and making the platform available to users. TRUST Principles were not yet explicitly applied, though early practices (open access to spectra and rich metadata) reflected transparency and responsibility. This stage was marked by secured funding, which supported the repository's launch and initial development.
Growth (2022-2024)	The repository expanded by increasing the number of datasets and data types, optimizing platform features, and engaging the user community. At this stage, the INFRA-ART team began exploring international standards and best practices, laying the foundation for alignment with FAIR and TRUST. Funding was available until 2022, after which the repository was maintained without financial support.
Maturity (2025)	With the core repository established, the focus shifted to governance, sustainability, and interoperability. In 2025, INFRA-ART formally adopted the TRUST Principles and embedded them into workflows through transparent policy documentation, and alignment with FAIR and EOSC standards. In this stage new funding was secured, including dedicated support for FAIRification and alignment with international standards.
Decline or Disruption (future risks)	Although not currently applicable, potential risks include funding gaps or rapid changes in technical infrastructure.
Reinvest or Sunet (future strategy)	INFRA-ART plans for reinvestment, with priorities including EOSC-compliant technical infrastructure, semantic web/linked data integration, and eventual CoreTrustSeal certification. In parallel, the repository aims to update its scientific content on an ongoing basis to remain relevant and valuable for the heritage science community.

Outcomes

- How does the organization/repository benefit from the implementation or use of the TRUST Principles?
 Implementing the TRUST Principles has strengthened INFRA-ART's governance, transparency, and reliability, making it a trusted resource for the heritage science community. We have seen an increase in data access and reuse, which aligns with the mission of our service and enhances its potential to attract continued support from funders.
- How has the implementation or use of the TRUST Principles impacted your organization/repository developmental roadmap?
 TRUST clarified priorities for sustainability, interoperability, and certification, guiding EOSC alignment and long-term planning.

- Are the TRUST Principles communicated to your wider repository community?
Yes, through the data governance framework, repository documentation, and the INFRA-ART blog.
- Do you believe the repository is more trustworthy after implementing or using the TRUST Principles?
Yes. The adoption of TRUST has made the INFRA-ART data service more transparent, accountable, and sustainable, increasing stakeholder confidence in its data integrity, governance, and long-term usability.
- Do you plan to move past the TRUST Principles and obtain certification for your organization/repository?
Yes, we are considering to apply for a CoreTrustSeal certification in the future (2026/2027).

References

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